

Transmediality and Colonial Diplomacy: The Berlin Conference (1884-1885) Through Diplomatic Correspondence, “Livre Jaunes” and the French Press

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Introduction

The 1880s marked a major turning point in the history of the French press and diplomacy. As the 1881 law enshrined freedom of the press and the industrialization of printing techniques led to the emergence of a new era of “newspaper civilization” (Kalifa et al. 2011), colonial tensions between European powers intensified, culminating in the Berlin Conference. Held from November 1884 to February 1885, the Conference brought together 14 major European powers, as well as the United States, with the aim of settling these disputes and establishing a legal framework for the effective occupation of African territory (De Courcel 1988).

While the economic and legal aspects of the Berlin Conference have been the subject of various studies (Förster et al. 1988; Craven 2015; Kumar 2016), its media dimension remains little explored, with the exception of Bendikat's work (1988). Similarly, the “Livres jaunes”, though crucial in mediating diplomatic information, have been neglected by academic research especially in terms of their interaction with the press. These series of publications of French diplomatic documents introduced in 1856, served as an official account of “France's foreign policy, as part of a controlled information effort aimed more particularly at French parliamentarians and opinion leaders, and at foreign cabinets”(Ministère de l'Europe et des Affaires étrangères n.d.).

To fill these gaps in existing literature, our study draws on a corpus of primary sources covering three distinct stages in the circulation of colonial diplomatic information: diplomatic correspondence from the reference work “Documents on the Berlin West African Conference and Related Subjects, 1884-1885” (Gavin and Betley 1973), the *Livre Jaune* published by the Ministry of Foreign Affairs in October 1884 (France Ministère des affaires étrangères 1884), and a selection of articles from 13 French newspapers of the period. Mobilizing the concepts of transmediality and entangled media history developed by Cronqvist and Hilgert (2017), we examine how diplomatic correspondence, initially confidential, were transformed into public documents through the *Livre Jaune*, and then reinterpreted by the French press. This approach, highlighting the dynamic interdependence of media across institutional and political boundaries, helps shed light on the mediatization mechanisms of colonial diplomacy and the construction of public opinion in late 19th-century France.

The Construction of the Diplomatic Narrative: From Correspondence to the *Livre Jaune*

The analysis of our corpus reveals a complex system of reciprocal influences between different media, showing how colonial diplomatic information circulates according to a dynamic of appropriation and transformation that highlights the constant interactions between the political sphere, the press and public opinion (Marc 1997).

The private correspondence between Jules Ferry and his ambassador in Berlin, Baron de Courcel, testifies to the constant attention paid to the reactions of French public opinion. In a letter dated 12 December 1884 to Courcel, Ferry is very aware of the risks of any concessions that might undermine France's colonial interests and provoke a justified outcry from public opinion (Gavin and Betley

1973). Courcel voices these same concerns with, Hatzfeldt, German State Secretary for Foreign Affairs, in a letter dated 5 December 1884, pointing to the challenges of convincing French public opinion on the practical results of the Franco-German entente. He cites in particular a “bitterly” critical article published in the *Journal des Débats*, pointing out that: “The government can only be embarrassed by attacks thus sustained.” (Gavin and Betley 1973)

The constant concern for public opinion had also a direct influence on the conduct of negotiations at the Conference, as illustrated by a telegram sent by Courcel to Ferry on November 22, 1884. In this message, the ambassador reports on his exchanges with Dr. Busch, a German Diplomat. Courcel describes drawing his interlocutor's attention to the resistance Ferry might encounter from French public opinion if he pushed concessions too far, pointing to the risk of a “movement of ideas contrary to our arrangements” likely to “occur in Parliament” and “prevent the ratification of the Conference” (Gavin and Betley 1973). This example illustrates how the media dimension and its echoes in public debate can constitute a significant constraint on diplomatic action.

The transition from these confidential correspondences to the *Livre Jaune* is therefore a delicate exercise in colonial narrative construction. A detailed analysis of the *Livre Jaune* “Affaires du Congo et de l’Afrique occidentale” published before the Berlin Conference, reveals an editorial strategy based on several mechanisms. The first level of construction takes place in the selection of documents: over the period 1882-1884, only 28 documents are retained for publication. Beyond this selective process, the organization of the *Livre Jaune* itself contributes to the construction of a coherent narrative. The chronological presentation of documents is designed to demonstrate the logical progression of French colonial enterprises, from the De Brazza mission to the Berlin Conference. The documents are carefully chosen to highlight certain narrative axes: the legitimacy of French action, its continuity, its “civilizing mission”, its moderation in the face of Portuguese pretensions, and the agreement with Germany for a conference presented as the natural outcome of this policy.

The “silences”, however, in this official narrative are significant: internal tensions, doubts about German strategy, and domestic political considerations are systematically erased from this public record. This process of erasure reflects a deliberate desire to shape a smooth, coherent image of French diplomatic action, while concealing the hesitations, disagreements and pressures that may have permeated it behind the scenes.

The Press vs the *Livre Jaune*: Colonial Diplomacy Under Scrutiny

This desire to control the diplomatic image was met with a complex and diverse media reception, as shown by the analysis of French press reactions to the publication of the *Livre Jaune* in 14 October 1884. The study of this reception highlights not only the diversity of editorial positions, but above all what Cronqvist and Hilgert (2017) describe as the “dynamic interconnectedness of media across [...] institutional and political boundaries.”

The flow of diplomatic information follows a pattern in which the official document becomes the starting point for a multi-level media conversation. The first level corresponds to the announcement and factual presentation of the *Livre Jaune*. *Le Monde* opened this media cycle on October 13, preparing its readers for the publication. *Le Petit Journal*, *La Justice* and *Le Matin* followed a similar approach on October 14 and 15, favoring a descriptive presentation that emphasized the technical nature of the document (28 items) and its period of coverage (1882-1884), as well as a selective reproduction of its content. This introductory function is soon supplemented by a second, more in-depth level of analysis. *Le Temps* and *Le Figaro* stand out for their methodical, exhaustive reading of the document over several issues. *La Croix* (October 16) adds to this reading, placing particular emphasis on the issues surrounding Savorgnan de Brazza's expedition.

A third level of media interaction takes the form of direct criticism of the diplomatic document. Over three issues (October 16-19), *La Gazette du Centre* launches an acerbic critique describing the publication as “un truc” of Jules Ferry “to explain his good relations with Germany.” *Le Combat* (October 16-18) took the critical analysis a step further, denouncing “cuts” and “disguise of truth”. The *Journal Des Débats* (October 15 and 20) adds a more technical dimension to this criticism, identifying precisely the gaps in coverage of certain important negotiations. The question

of the Franco-German alliance in particular gives rise to divergent interpretations. L'Anjou was particularly virulent in its criticism, devoting three articles (October 17, 22 and 27) to denouncing what it perceived as a surrender to Germany. Le Radical (October 16) follows this critical line, questioning diplomatic leaks, particularly a letter from the Livre Jaune prematurely published in Le Figaro, suggesting possible orchestration by either Ferry or Bismarck. In contrast, Le Patriote Albigeois (October 19) defends the agreements as balanced and profitable for France.

The publication of the Livre Jaune was part of a sophisticated media ecosystem in which different types of publication interacted. La Croix (October 16) and Le Figaro illustrate this flow of information particularly well, crossing official sources with commentaries from the French and foreign press. A true media conversation developed: Le Radical (October 16) echoed the analyses of Le Journal des Débats, while Le Combat took up and criticized the positions of Le Temps.

Conclusion

This study reveals the complexity of interactions between diplomacy and the media in the age of imperialism. A cross-analysis of diplomatic correspondence, the Livre Jaune and its reception in the French press reveals the emergence of a dynamic public space, where different narratives are developed and confronted on the basis of a common documentary matrix. The case of the Berlin Conference illustrates how the state attempted to shape and control diplomatic colonial discourse while simultaneously coping with press criticism that often challenged its official narrative. Far from being mere relays of official information, newspapers appear to be players in their own right in the colonial debate, capable of influencing representations and decisions of those in power. This transmedia approach opens up new perspectives for rethinking relations between diplomacy, colonial propaganda and public opinion in the late 19th-century.

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